

A SHORTCUT TO SPACE TRAVEL: THE SPACE TUNNEL**Abbasov V.***Baku State University, student.***Bayramova T.***Candidate of physical and mathematical sciences, docent.**Baku State University**Baku, Republic of Azerbaijan.*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14499280>**Abstract**

The causes of gravitational phenomena in the universe have always been an object of interest. In the end, it became clear that the reasons for the formation of the gravitational field cannot be fully explained by 3-dimensional space. As A. Einstein rightly noted, the properties of the gravitational field should be characterized by 4-dimensional space. A. Einstein combined this idea, that is, the results about the gravitational field, in his general theory of relativity. In modern science, the events occurring in the Universe are explained on the basis of the solutions obtained from A. Einstein's theory of relativity. In addition, an issue arising from the solutions of the theory of relativity is the existence of a space tunnel. A space tunnel is one of the shortest ways to travel through the Universe. In the presented work, modern approaches to the existence of the space tunnel were considered. At the same time, new ideas about the possibility of creating a space tunnel with our modern technological capabilities were mentioned. In the end, theoretical approaches to effectively use the positive results of the experience were touched upon.

Keywords: gravitational field, general relativity, gravitational waves, space tunnel, large adron collider.

Introduction. The phenomenon of attraction in the universe has always been an object of interest. Until the beginning of the 20th century, it was known to science that there is a force of gravity between objects in the Universe, but the reason for this was not completely clear. At the beginning of the 20th century, A. Einstein proved that space and time are a single entity through the theory of special relativity. Along with this, A. Einstein established the theory of general relativity and integrated this theory in the field of gravity. According to A. Einstein, space and time are complete and look like a piece of material. Any object with mass bends this material. A hole is formed in the bent part, and thus the objects with a small mass circulate around the objects

with a large mass [1]. According to A. Einstein, this material exists in 4-dimensional space. In many theoretical studies, A. Einstein was found to be right [2]. Another conclusion from general relativity is the question of the existence of space tunnels. The space tunnel is an object that connects different points of space and time, and its existence depends on the special solution of the equations of A. Einstein's theory of relativity. A space tunnel can connect billions of light years or more, parallel Universes, or different points in time. This is hypothetical, the space tunnel has not yet been discovered. However, mathematical and theoretical calculations show that they may exist.

The concept of a space tunnel was first proposed by Ludwig Flamm in 1916. Looking at the equations of Einstein's theory of general relativity, Flamm pointed out that a celestial body, which he named a white hole, with the exact opposite properties of black holes, could theoretically be possible. He thought it might be possible to build a bridge between a white hole and a black hole. In 1935, A. Einstein and Nathan Rosen proposed the existence of spatial bridges in space-time using the theory of general relativity. According to their thinking, these bridges act as a tunnel that bends space and creates a short distance between two different points. These tunnels have two parts: entrance and exit [3]. It is clear from this that an object entering this tunnel in space will reach the other side faster than at a normal distance. Since space and time are complete, we can also note that the space tunnel connects not only two spaces, but also two times. Therefore, the space tunnel can connect a certain moment in time with the previous time.

Setting the issue. Let's look at some cases of general relativity. There must be a black hole on either side of the space tunnel. But naturally, a black hole cannot

Therefore, there must be a defect created in space in the part where the gravitational waves are detected. As a result of research, these waves were discovered for the first time in black holes. It turns out that black holes are actually defects in space.

From this point of view, one side of the space tunnel cannot be a black hole. Black holes bend space so much that time passes more slowly around it, and at the same time defects appear in space. It can be said that kinks present in phase do not always cause defects. If

create a space tunnel by itself as a dying star collapses. Therefore, many scientists think that the space tunnel is only a part of a space in 4-dimensional space [4]. It is known that the whole phase is composed of vibrating strings. There is a continuous exchange of energy between these strings [5]. But in some cases, for example, during astronomical disasters, the space between these strings becomes too large for their dimensions, and at this time, depending on the distance, the energy exchange between the strings disappears, so this part of space cannot restore itself. At this time, as a result of this defect in the 3-dimensional space, matter transitions from the 4-dimensional space [6]. Since everything that exists in 3-dimensional space has mass and shape, every object that moves into this space gains these properties, or rather, loses some additional properties. As we mentioned above, it is already known that the gravitational field exists in 4-dimensional space. These material entities that exist in 4-dimensional space cannot be seen or felt. As a result of an astronomical catastrophe, the observed gravitational field shifts from 4-dimensional space to our space. It was possible to observe this field as it took the form of a wave.

values close to the energy released by the explosion are obtained, some faultless bending will occur in the cavity. The mechanism of creating a space tunnel can be justified in this way. To visualize the space tunnel more clearly, it is necessary to imagine space as a 2-dimensional space. The space tunnel will now appear as just a hole. However, beneath the 2-dimensional level lies a 3-dimensional cylindrical bridge. The end of this tunnel will appear as a hole at any point in 2D space. Actually, the space tunnel looks like these.

Solution of problem. A space tunnel can allow any object to travel at speeds greater than the speed of light without exceeding the speed of light. Through space tunnels, it is possible to travel to greater distances in the Universe in a short time. This fact shows the importance of detecting tunnels. It may be possible to create these tunnels through existing devices. From what we mentioned above, it is possible to create a space tunnel if we can get an energy level close to the energy of a star at the moment of explosion. The length of the space tunnel will vary depending on the price of this energy. Therefore, it is necessary to look at the events

where it is possible to obtain energy close to this energy level. This includes the great energy generated by the collision of particles. The European nuclear research center, where the properties of particles are studied in detail, is located on the border of France and Switzerland. The largest device in this center is the Large Hadron Collider. The length of this facility is 26.7 km and it is located at a depth of 100 meters. The Large Hadron Collider is designed to collide protons with an energy of 14 TeV [7]. In 2012, such a collision took place, and as a result, a temperature of 5.5 trillion degrees Celsius appeared [8].

Since the value of thermal energy per wire at this temperature is much greater than the exchange energy between the wires, a defect will occur. At this time, all the energy will be transferred from one space to another. That is, this heat will disappear in a short time. This theoretical fact is consistent with the obtained result. If this energy were released piecemeal, then a ripple would be observed in space. Thus, it will be possible to create a space tunnel.

Results. Like the Large Hadron Collider, but smaller, let's place two identical devices parallel to each

other at a certain distance L and collide protons inside these devices at the same time. Release large amounts of absorbed energy evenly around the unit. At this time, there will be a significant energy difference between the internal and external parts of the device. This energy difference indicates the ratio of the curvature of the cavity at the edges of the device to the interior. A tunnel of length L will be formed between the devices as a result of the energy exchange as a result of the touching of the spatial parts wrapped by both devices.

It is now possible to study the movement of the object in this system. If we send the object outside this system to the same distance L with speed V , the time taken for the object to cover this distance will be t . Now let's send the same body into this system we have prepared. This trip, the object we send with the same speed V will cover the distance L between the devices in time t' . These times will differ from each other by a billionth of a second. As a result of analyzing the results obtained

from the experiment, it is possible to determine the relationship between the released energy and the obtained time period Δt . This relationship will allow us to determine the energy needed to travel an arbitrary distance in the Universe in a short period of time. Attempts to create a space tunnel in space will facilitate the exploration of the Universe by humans despite its infinite size.

As the technology develops, we will be able to take a closer look at the still unsolved celestial objects in the Universe through the space tunnel. In this regard, the efforts made in this direction will contribute to science both theoretically and experimentally. Astronomy

will become not only an observational science, but also an experimental science.

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